

Electron-induced and electron-capture dissociation in data-dependent acquisition mode performed on the Omnitrap platform coupled to an Orbitrap MS

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The Omnitrap platform coupled to Q Exactive HF and EASY-nLC 1000

Fasmatech's OmniLab

NanoSpray Flex™ Ion Source
(Thermo Fisher Scientific)

C18 PepSep nLC column
(25cm×75µm, 3µm)

Electron-based Activation in Segment Q5 of the Omnitrap Platform

35 eV
electron energy
for optimum EID

event sequence in DDA MS2 ExD

Data-Depended Acquisition in the Omnitrap Q Exactive HF Platform

BSA Digest H₂O:FA:ACN 92:5:3 v/v
Injection: 2μL of C=100 fmol/μL

Max Injection Time = 200ms
AGC Target = 5e⁶
Dynamic Exclusion: 10s
Top10

NL:
4.85E9
TIC M S
220401_BSA_dd
M S2_HCD_100m
n_IT200_AGC5
e6_DEx10_01

NL:
5.43E9
TIC M S
220331_BSA_dd
M S2_EID_100mi
n_IT200_AGC5e
6_DEx10_01

NL:
4.82E9
TIC M S
220331_BSA_dd
M S2_ECD_100mi
n_IT200_AGC5
e6_DEx10_01

Data Analysis

LC-MS/MS .RAW

PD extension

Consensus step:
CWF_Basic_Annotation

Processing step:
PWF_OT_Basic_SequestHT

All primary fragments (a, b, c, x, y, z) are included in the ExD (x=I, C) search, while the HCD search is limited to a, b and y.

Fasmatech's PD extension software recalculates and reassigns fragments to all MS2 peptide mass spectra identified in PD.

2+

Enhancing Sequence Coverage, Complementarity and side chain information

3+

Enhancing Sequence Coverage, Complementarity and side chain information

Complementarity vs Peptide Charge State

HCD 2+ 60%

HCD 3+ 39%

HCD 4+ 24%

EID 2+ 77%

EID 3+ 71%

EID 4+ 57%

ECD 2+ 44%

ECD 3+ 76%

ECD 4+ 62%

Summary Table & Results

Exp	BSA PSMs	Total PSMs	MS/MS	Peptides	Sequence Coverage (%)
HCD	2044	3241	18907	76	89
EID	1600	3094	14608	72	88
ECD	1214	2598	13073	63	82

Max Injection time = 200 ms
 AGC Target=5e⁶
 Dynamic Exclusion=10s
 Top10

Sequence Coverage

Complementarity

ECD

The example of FKDLGEEHFK

ECD**z=2+****GRAVY Index**

hydrophilic

hydrophobic

EID

The example of FKDLGEEHFK

└─┘	d	└─┘	a
└─┘	v	└─┘	x
└─┘	w	└─┘	b
└─┘		└─┘	y
└─┘		└─┘	c
└─┘		└─┘	z

Leucine & Isoleucine w diagnostic fragments

■ # Leu + Ile ■ EID w ■ ECD w

2+

3+

4+

49%

63%

EID fragments with neutral side chain losses

LCVLHEK 2+
*carbamidomethyl

AA	Side chain cleavage position			
	$C_\alpha \neq C_\beta$	$C_\beta \neq C_\gamma$	$C_\gamma \neq C_\delta$	$C_\delta \neq C_\epsilon$
K		C_3H_9N		CH_5N
R			$C_2H_6N_3 (\bullet)$	CH_3N_3
Y		C_6H_6O $C_6H_5O (\bullet)$ $C_6H_5O (\bullet)$		
E	$C_2H_4O_2$ $C_2H_4O_2$			
M	$C_3H_7S (\bullet)$ C_3H_8S			
T	$C_2H_5O (\bullet)$			

Comparing ExD with EThcD on the Fusion Lumos

NL:
1.70E9
TIC MS
20211006_
L1_05_BS
A_EThcD_
05

EID 2+ 98%

ECD 2+ 92%

EThcD 2+ 89%

EID 3+ 95%

ECD 3+ 96%

EThcD 3+ 88%

EID 4+ 86%

ECD 4+ 94%

EThcD 4+ 83%

Omnitrap platform coupled to
Exploris 480 Mass Spectrometer

Electron-based Activation in Segment Q5 of the Orbitrap Platform

Optimized event sequence for maximum speed in DDA MS2 ExD

EID reaction time: 35 ms
Transfer time from and to HCD cell: 35 ms
OMNITRAP Processing cycle: **~70 ms**
processing in HCD – c-trap: 10 ms
max Injection time: 35 ms
ORBITRAP Processing cycle: **~45 ms**

~9 Hz

ECD reaction time: 100 ms
Transfer time from and to HCD cell: 35 ms
OMNITRAP Processing cycle: **~135 ms**
processing in HCD – c-trap: 10 ms
max Injection time: 35 ms
ORBITRAP Processing cycle: **~45 ms**

~6 Hz

Orbitrap Mass Resolving Power: 15k, 32 ms

Extending the analysis to complex protein samples – HeLa digest

Frags. Method	ddMS2 AGC target	ddMS2 max IT (ms)	electron reaction time (ms)	scan rate (scans/s)	Proteins <i>High confidence</i>	Peptides* (± 10 ppm)	MS/MS*	PSMs*
HCD	1e6	35	-	~ 16.4	3747	31438 / 70465	42903 / 89739	41783 / 88432
EID	1e6	35	35	~ 8.5	3416	21342 / 41767	23255 / 48909	22879 / 46683
ECD	1e6	35	100	~ 5.9	2482	13676 / 23786	15242 / 35397	15169 / 26302

* Peptides, MS/MS and PSMs refer to “high-confidence protein identifications” using both medium and high confidence peptides

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